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Sludge Pasteurization with Solar Water Heaters: An Off-Grid Electrically Controlled Solution

Author : Recep Polat

Supervisors : Prof. Elizabeth Tilley

Dr. Jakub Tkaczuk

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CONTENTS

List of Tables	vii
List of Figures	x
Abstract	xi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Sanitation as a Global Challenge	1
1.2 Anaerobic Digestion as a Treatment Method	2
1.3 Digestate Post Treatment Methods	2
1.4 Thermal Inactivation and Safety Zones	3
1.5 Modeling Non-Isothermal Processes: The Bigelow Model	3
1.6 Previous Work and Research Questions	5
2 Methods	7
2.1 Site Description	7
2.2 Electronics	9
2.2.1 Infrastructure Electronics	9
2.2.2 Solar Heater Electronics	10
2.2.3 Research Hut Computer	12
2.3 Treatment Algorithms	12
2.3.1 Algorithm 1: Naive Threshold Control	14
2.3.2 Algorithm 2: ERT Calculating Algorithm	15
2.4 Instrumentation and Data Collection	17
2.4.1 Temperature Measurements	17
2.4.2 Flow Measurements	17
2.4.3 Heat Exchanger Efficiency Measurements	18
2.4.4 Illuminance and Irradiation	18
2.4.5 Sample Analysis	19

3	Results	21
3.1	Thermal Performance And Dynamics	21
3.1.1	Stratification	21
3.1.2	Nocturnal Heat Loss	22
3.2	Heat Exchanger Validation	24
3.3	Current Consumption	24
3.4	Electronics Heat Profile	25
3.5	Effluent Throughput	26
3.6	Microbiological Results	28
3.7	Cost Analysis	29
3.8	Discussion	31
3.8.1	Thermal Dynamics and Pasteurization Efficiency	31
3.8.2	Power and Heat Management	31
3.8.3	Controls	31
3.8.4	Microbiological Results	31
4	Conclusions and Outlook	33
	Bibliography	35

LIST OF TABLES

3.1	Randomly selected nocturnal heat loss parameters from dataset.	23
3.2	Daily Hydraulic Throughput	27
3.3	Comparison of <i>E. coli</i> and Total Coliform concentrations in the Solar Heater and Effluent Tower (Samples tested within 3 days of collection). The E.Coli and Total Coliform concentrations are given by the number of colony forming units per 100ml.	29
3.4	A cost breakdown of the solar heater and the parts around it. Next to the component names are what country they were acquired in. E stands for Europe, C stands for China. Both of these are online orders. M stands for Malawi and these were either bought from the markets in Mzuzu, or in direct contact with sellers.	30

LIST OF FIGURES

1.1	A time-temperature graph that depicts the deactivation zones for different groups of pathogens from Espinosa et al. Espinosa et al., 2020 . Plot <i>a</i> on the left-hand side shows the found minimum time-temperature curves for at least 90% reduction. Plot <i>b</i> on the right-hand side visualizes the findings corresponding to an at least 99.9% reduction.	4
1.2	Tank temperatures throughout a typical March day in Mzuzu. The difference of temperature throughout the day exceeded 20C	4
2.1	A drone photo of the biogas site in Mzuzu. What is visible are the following: A: water and effluent reservoirs, B: effluent distribution box, C: solar heater system, D: Sistema 40 biogas digester, E: inlet pool, F: Sistema 12 biogas digester, G: Sistema 30 biogas digester that is in series with the Sistema 12, H: effluent outflow manhole and buffer tanks, I: research hut, J: waste pool	8
2.2	A visual simplified diagram of the effluent flow.	9
2.3	Infrastructure Electronics	10
2.4	Solar heater Electronics Simplified Diagram	11
2.5	In a watertight box, the lead-acid battery and the printed circuit board that contains the battery management system, the microcontroller, the motor drivers for the solenoids, the radio module, and connectors to the rest of the elements. . . .	12
2.6	Composite view of the Solar Water Heater unit	13
2.7	Our UI dashboard hosted on the Thingsboard Cloud	13
2.8	A comparison of linear interpolation and logarithmic fitting on an example set of measured D-values.	16
2.9	The heat exchanger. Also visible are the thermowells for inserting thermal sensors, the inlet solenoid valve on the right-hand side, and the electronics box in the background.	18

- 3.1 Plot that shows the temperature measurements taken from 3 distinct positions at the tank on 4 consecutive days in late March. The measurements show strong stratification. 22
- 3.2 An efficiency vs. time plot characterizing the heat exchanger. The max efficiency point is marked with a red cross, and the average efficiency over the experiment period (9 minutes) is found to be 0.55 25
- 3.3 The battery voltage over a late March day. The naive algorithm is used where the tank temperature threshold is 70°C, and the valves are not opened if the MCU die temperature exceeds 50°C. The red zones are when the valves are opened. . 26
- 3.4 The plot of the flow sensor readings converted to *L/min*. This plot is taken from the same day as Figure 3.3 27
- 3.5 Mzuzu mean daily sunshine hours for every month, derived from data collected 1961-1990 (*Mzuzu Climate Normals Measured Between 1961-1990* 1998 28

ABSTRACT

In low-income regions of Sub-Saharan Africa, limited access to safe sanitation poses significant risks to human health and the environment. While biogas digesters stabilize waste and recover energy, the resulting effluent requires further treatment before safe disposal. This study evaluates the feasibility of using a commercial solar heater (RiWatt IronMan-150L) to pasteurize anaerobic digester effluent in Mzuzu, Malawi. Using off-grid electronic controls, the system regulates effluent flow based on internal thermal states to maximize throughput while ensuring pathogen inactivation. Thermal analysis revealed significant vertical stratification, with a stagnant cold pocket below the vacuum tube inlets. While pasteurization temperatures above 80°C were achieved, microbiological analysis using two field methods yielded incoherent results, suggesting a need for more reliable reference protocols. The total system cost was calculated at around 860 CHF, which is higher than previous similar studies and may limit viability in low-income contexts without further cost-reduction or economies of scale. Future work should focus on improving heat insulation, refining control algorithms, and addressing the discrepancies in microbiological field testing.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Sanitation as a Global Challenge

Sanitation services refer to the management of excreta from the facilities used by individuals, through emptying and transport of excreta for treatment and eventual discharge or use, as defined by the United Nations and the World Health Organization (Agberemi *et al.*, 2020). Although declared as a human right, 35% of urban populations and 54% of rural populations in the world still lacked access to safely managed sanitation services in 2022 (United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2023). Stemming from the fact that human waste contains a number of pathogenic microorganisms (Feachem *et al.*, 1981), a lack of sanitation services has been shown to have serious health impacts, including malnutrition, diarrhoea, helminth infections, schistosomiasis, trachoma et cetera, which are thought to have caused close to a million deaths worldwide in 2016 (Agberemi *et al.*, 2020).

Studies have shown that improved sanitation can have a major impact on the prevention of these diseases. Improved sanitation, meaning either connection to a sewage system, septic tanks, ventilated pit latrines or pit latrines with a concrete slab, can reduce the prevalence of diarrhoea by 32-36% (Brown, Cairncross, and Ensink, 2013). Because of the necessary investment to build this kind of infrastructure, mostly low and middle income countries' residents are subject to unsafely managed human waste and all the issues that are caused by it (Hyun *et al.*, 2019). As an alternative to conventional sewage, on-site sanitation technologies (pit latrines, composting toilets...) are adequate for low- and middle-income countries, but the lack of transport of the waste imposes the limitation that the waste liquids disperse into the surrounding soil and the solids accumulate. In densely populated areas, this makes on-site sanitation infeasible, since it carries the risk of contaminating drinking water sources (Paterson, Mara, and Curtis, 2007). In order to kill the pathogens and make the waste safe for disposal, it is necessary to subject the collected waste to some kind of post-treatment method either on-site, or elsewhere at a collection site.

1.2 Anaerobic Digestion as a Treatment Method

Anaerobic digestion is a biological process where microorganisms break down biodegradable material in the absence of oxygen (Alfa *et al.*, 2014). In the context of biowaste, AD serves as a primary stabilization method by converting complex carbons into biogas, a mixture of methane and carbon dioxide, and a nutrient-rich liquid known as digestate.

This process stabilizes waste by significantly reducing the chemical oxygen demand (COD) and volatile solids (VS), thereby mitigating odors and preventing the uncontrolled release of greenhouse gases (Safieddin Ardebili, 2020). Furthermore, AD facilitates nutrient transformation; organically bound nitrogen is converted into plant-available ammonium, making the resulting digestate a potentially valuable biofertilizer for local agriculture (Samoraj *et al.*, 2022).

Studies indicate that while AD can achieve a moderate reduction in bacterial indicators, enteric pathogens—particularly viruses, protozoan cysts, and helminth eggs (such as *Ascaris*)—often survive the hydraulic retention time of the digester. Consequently, the effluent exiting a biogas system remains a biological hazard, requiring secondary post-treatment before it can be safely handled or used in soil amendment (Álvarez-Fraga *et al.*, 2025).

1.3 Digestate Post Treatment Methods

To completely inactivate the effluent pathogens, several methods exist, including chemical, radiation-based, physical filtration and pasteurization (Muraca, Yu, and Goetz, 1990) (Lanrewaju *et al.*, 2022). Of all of these, thermal pasteurization remains a preferable method due to its effectiveness and simplicity in operation. Pasteurization is the treatment of organic materials with heat to bring them up to temperatures usually below 100°C in order to eliminate pathogens (Peng *et al.*, 2013).

A number of methods to supply heat exist. In a low-income environment, the following could be considered:

- Biogas combustion: previous research has shown that biogas produced through the anaerobic digestion of biowaste can be used to further pasteurize it after the anaerobic processes (Forbis-Stokes *et al.*, 2016).
- Electric resistance heating: in a context where an abundant and consistent supply of electricity is available, the effluent can be heated up using electricity
- Solar thermal collection: in a context of abundant sunlight, solar collectors can be used to bring the effluent to high temperatures (Lotti, 2025) (Grimont, 2024).

Solar thermal collectors have the advantages of being technologically simple. Examples exist where commercial solar collectors have been used to pasteurize drinking water (Carielo Da Silva, Tiba, and Calazans, 2016). Due to being widely available in low-income countries and due to their decentralized operation capability, these commercial solar collectors are a suitable solution for low-income rural areas where sanitation is a pressing problem (Agberemi *et al.*, 2020).

1.4 Thermal Inactivation and Safety Zones

The inactivation of microorganisms through heat is a function of both temperature and exposure time. This relationship is non-linear: as temperature increases linearly, the time required for a specific level of pathogen reduction decreases exponentially.

An early and impactful attempt to define safety boundaries for excreta management was established by (Feachem *et al.*, 1981). They proposed a "safety zone" based on empirical observations of various pathogens (bacteria, viruses, and helminths). However, these zones were broad and did not specify the exact magnitude of reduction (e.g. 90% vs. 99.9%).

More recent research refined these criteria through a meta-analysis, establishing specific time-temperature combinations required to achieve $1 \log_{10}$ (90%) and $3 \log_{10}$ (99.9%) reductions (Espinosa *et al.*, 2020). Figure 1.1 is an excerpt from the same paper. It shows the time-temperature curves for different reduction ratios and for different strands of pathogens. Their research has shown that temperatures and exposure times for a given ratio of pathogen reduction is higher than estimated by previous research. Hence it is advisable to adhere to stricter requirements in pasteurizer design.

1.5 Modeling Non-Isothermal Processes: The Bigelow Model

In using a solar collector for thermal pasteurization, one faces the difficulty of applying the safety criteria such as those recommended by established research (Espinosa *et al.*, 2020). The reason is that the temperature in a solar heated chamber is determined by uncontrollable external factors, unlike in an industrial pasteurizer. As a result, the temperature varies significantly throughout the day, as seen in Figure 1.2. This requires a mathematical model to account for non-isothermal conditions (Nunes, Swartzel, and Ollis, 1993).

The gist of this mathematical approach is integrating the effect of varying temperatures over time to reach a metric that quantifies the cumulative lethal effect on the pathogens. This can be

Figure 1.1. A time-temperature graph that depicts the deactivation zones for different groups of pathogens from Espinosa et al. [Espinosa et al., 2020](#). Plot *a* on the left-hand side shows the found minimum time-temperature curves for at least 90% reduction. Plot *b* on the right-hand side visualizes the findings corresponding to an at least 99.9% reduction.

Figure 1.2. Tank temperatures throughout a typical March day in Mzuzu. The difference of temperature throughout the day exceeded 20C

achieved using the Bigelow Model, which builds on the finding that thermal death time curves are logarithmic in nature ([Bigelow, 1921](#)). This logarithmic behavior is visible in Figure 1.1. By establishing the relationship between a change in temperature vs. the resulting change in necessary retention time around a reference temperature, one can extrapolate different temperatures and find the necessary retention time for them. And the thermal load can be modeled to simply be proportional to the inverse of the necessary retention time.

Specifically, we will use the mathematical model introduced in [Nunes, Swartzel, and Ollis, 1993](#). We define the lethal rate (L) at any given temperature T is defined as:

$$L = 10^{(T-T_{ref})/z} \quad (1.1)$$

Where:

- T : The actual measured temperature
- T_{ref} : The target reference temperature
- z : The temperature change required to produce a 10-fold change in the inactivation rate (the z-value). This is an experimental value that we based on the work by Espinosa et al. [Espinosa et al., 2020](#) and the published experimental data linked to that study

In a continuous time system, we define *equivalent retention time* ϵ as:

$$\epsilon = \int_0^t 10^{\frac{T(t)-T_{ref}}{z}} dt \quad (1.2)$$

And in discrete time this corresponds to:

$$\epsilon_{total} = \sum_{i=1}^n \Delta t \cdot 10^{\frac{T_i-T_{ref}}{z}} \quad (1.3)$$

where Δt is the discrete time step size.

1.6 Previous Work and Research Questions

The present study builds upon a series of consecutive research projects aimed at developing a decentralized, solar-powered sludge pasteurization system for off-grid contexts in Sub-Saharan Africa. The first prototype, developed by [Grimont, 2024](#) in Kiambu, Kenya, established the proof-of-concept but faced significant challenges; the system failed to reach target temperatures during low-irradiance seasons, and the mechanical thermostatic valve intended for regulation proved unreliable, preventing complete treatment cycles.

A subsequent iteration by [Cinar, 2025](#) moved the project to Nakuru, Kenya, to leverage higher solar irradiance and replaced the failed thermostatic valve with a continuous flow configuration. While this version successfully achieved *E. coli* inactivation under favorable summer conditions, the testing was limited to peak irradiance periods, leaving the system's performance under fluctuating seasonal conditions and thermal loss profiles largely unverified.

The most recent advancement by [Lotti, 2025](#) in Nakuru focused on hardware optimization, introducing a redesigned counter-flow heat exchanger and a nighttime flow-closure mechanism that significantly improved heat retention. While Lotti demonstrated that the system could achieve non-detectable levels of *E. coli* at constant flow rates, he identified the need for more sophisticated, autonomous control. He noted that the stochastic nature of solar energy makes

constant-flow treatment difficult to manage and proposed that future systems should regulate flow in real-time according to tank temperature and the Equivalent Retention Time (ERT).

The current research addresses these identified gaps by automating effluent flow by implementing a multiple-input-single-output control framework running on a microcontroller platform. With the goal of reaching non-detectable pathogen levels and maximizing throughput, various control methodologies will be investigated.

We aim to answer the following questions:

1. **How can we model the temperature stratification and convectional flows in the tank to be able to calculate the effective holding times in the tank?** In order to devise a control algorithm that takes into account the thermal load in different parts of the system, we need a realistic model of the temperature stratification and the convectional flows inside the system.
2. **What simple and effective control law should be implemented to yield a 99.9% reduction of pathogens?**
3. **What is the minimum number of sensors necessary to sufficiently identify the system?** To minimize cost and complexity, the lower the number of sensors the better. In this light, what sensor data is indispensable?
4. **Can the controller run entirely on solar panel collected energy?** Running off-grid is important for remote areas, which makes this an important goal.
5. **What is the minimum total bill of materials of a self-sufficient system for a given size of anaerobic digester in Mzuzu, Malawi? And what are the running costs?**

2 METHODS

2.1 Site Description

Since 2024, the Global Health Engineering lab at ETH Zurich has agreed with the Mzuzu City Council to operate a biogas research site in the Nkhorongo area of Mzuzu in Malawi. The research being done here aims to explore the use of biogas digester technology -well established in agricultural contexts- in human waste stabilization. The site is operated all year round by a team of Malawian technicians, who make sure that there is a steady inflow of feed into the digesters. This is done through a close collaboration with pit latrine emptiers, a slaughterhouse, and vendors from a close-by vegetable market.

The biogas digesters produce two outputs. The first output is biogas, which is transported through pressure relief buckets and H_2S filters to gas stoves where locals cook every day. The biogas aspect of the setup is outside the scope of this project. The second output is a liquid effluent, which gets emptied into a waste pool adjacent to the research site. This research aims to employ a commercial solar water heater to treat this effluent with heat collected from the sun and kill the pathogens in it.

The solar water heater that we used is a RiWatt IronMan-150L that was sourced from a distributor in Lilongwe. Because we are not heating water in the solar **water** heater, it will be called **solar heater** from here on.

Figure 2.1 shows an aerial photo of the site. The system is fed with human waste from pit latrines, cow stomach contents, and vegetable remains, and the technicians keep a detailed log of the amount and kind of feed that goes into the system. The feed gets shredded at the site and mixed with water in the inlet pool (E in the image), from which they flow into the Sistema 12 (F in the image) and the Sistema 40 (D in the image) biogas digesters.

As visible in the aerial image, there are 2 alternative pathways the waste can travel through in the system. It is either through the Sistema 40, or first the Sistema 12 then the Sistema 30. The effluent flowing from the biogas digesters is first stored in buffer tanks (H in the image), then it flows through underground pipes into the effluent distribution system (B in the image).

From here they are pumped up to the effluent storage tank (A in the image, the one on the

Figure 2.1. A drone photo of the biogas site in Mzuzu. What is visible are the following: A: water and effluent reservoirs, B: effluent distribution box, C: solar heater system, D: Sistema 40 biogas digester, E: inlet pool, F: Sistema 12 biogas digester, G: Sistema 30 biogas digester that is in series with the Sistema 12, H: effluent outflow manhole and buffer tanks, I: research hut, J: waste pool

right). The effluent storage tank stands elevated on a tower, so the effluent can flow into the solar heater system (C in the image) with the help of gravity. The solar heater is placed such that the solar collector tubes are facing the north. This is due to the fact that Malawi is in the southern hemisphere, so a north-facing surface will see the most irradiation in total over the year.

If the effluent storage tank is full or the effluent distribution box cannot keep up with the incoming effluent flow, the effluent flows into the waste pool (J in the image). The research hut (I in the image) is where the infrastructure electronics are kept, and where the technicians conduct sample analyses.

Figure 2.2 shows a simplified diagram of the effluent flow through the system. Not mentioned in the previous paragraph are the filter and the heat exchanger. The filters are gravel buckets that are right at the outlet of the biogas digesters. These gravel buckets filter out the suspended solids in the effluent such as sand, undissolved fibers etc. This prevents the accumulation of these particles in piping elements and pumps and the resulting potential clogging. We made these ourselves using construction-grade gravel and sand. The heat exchanger helps collect the heat from the treated hot effluent leaving the solar heater and transfers it to the cold effluent entering the solar heater. In Figure 2.6c, one can see the heat exchanger and the

Figure 2.2. A visual simplified diagram of the effluent flow.

solar heater with its inlets and outlets. This is a commercial off-the-shelf unit with the product name *VEVOR EATB12*.

2.2 Electronics

The electronics at the site can be divided into 3 subgroups:

- Infrastructure electronics
- Solar heater electronics
- Research Hut Computer

Each of these will be elaborated separately in the section. The design files for all custom electronics and the accompanying software can be found in the project repository ([Polat, Tkaczuk, and Tilley, 2026](#)).

2.2.1 Infrastructure Electronics

The infrastructure electronics comprises:

- a flow sensor that measures the flow of the effluent flowing out of the effluent storage tank
- one analog level sensor that measures the fill level of the effluent storage tank
- one set of level switch and pump that enables effluent to be pumped up to the effluent storage tank when available
- one set of level switch and pump that detects when the effluent distribution box is flooded and ensures that it is evacuated

Figure 2.3. Infrastructure Electronics

The sensors and actuators of this system are directly connected to a microcontroller inside the research hut. This microcontroller continuously samples the sensors and controls the pumps, while periodically sending telemetry packets to the computer inside the research hut. These telemetry data are saved locally every 5 seconds, uploaded to a web UI every 5 minutes, and pushed to a git repository every hour. Here the git repository only contains measurement data, no code. Hence there is no version control associated with it.

2.2.2 Solar Heater Electronics

The electronics around the solar heater are the main focus of this research. As seen in Figure 2.4, a microcontroller is the centerpiece of this system. The system is built around an STM32L432 low-power microcontroller running Zephyr RTOS, connected to:

- a LoRa radio SoC for transmitting telemetry data,
- a range of temperature sensors around the solar heater (3 DS18B20 based sensors in the final version),
- motor drivers to power the solenoid valves that control the flow in and out of the solar heater (motor drivers were used to be able to modulate the solenoid current in order to reduce the current consumption),
- and the power section, highlighted in blue in Figure 2.4. The power section contains a lead-acid battery pack that is commonly found on motorcycles in Mzuzu. The battery that we found is sold as a 12V with a capacity of 6.5Ah, but these parameters should ideally be tested. The solar panel is a 30W module, which is also widely available in Mzuzu. And

Figure 2.4. Solar heater Electronics Simplified Diagram

these two are connected to the battery management system that charges the battery with the solar panels, and powers all the rest of the electronics while cutting off the power if the battery voltage gets critically low.

For compactness and durability, the solar heater electronics were placed on a custom printed circuit board as seen in Figure 2.5. This circuit board sits in a watertight box alongside the lead-acid battery, where the external cable connections enter the box through watertight tank connectors. Figure 2.6.c shows the placement of the electronics box and the solar panel with respect to the solar heater.

Also visible in this figure are the 2 solenoid valves and the 3 temperature sensors. There is one solenoid valve at the cold inlet of the heat exchanger that sits underneath the solar heater tank (refer to Figure 2.9), and one at the outlet of the tank on the left-hand side (refer to Figure 2.6b). And the temperature sensors are placed such that there is one at the bottom, one at the middle and one at the top of the solar heater tank, as seen in figures 2.6e, 2.6b, 2.6d.

The solar heater electronics have been designed to conserve as much energy as possible. The whole system goes to sleep in between activity phases, which is every 5 minutes. And the solenoids' drive current is modulated to reduce the energy consumption.

The solar panel has been placed so that the maximum amount of sunlight can be absorbed in the afternoon when the effluent temperatures are at high levels, but the sunlight is diminishing. Therefore, it is facing west. This is justified by the battery voltage level with respect to the tank temperatures and valve activity discussed in section 3.3.

Figure 2.5. In a watertight box, the lead-acid battery and the printed circuit board that contains the battery management system, the microcontroller, the motor drivers for the solenoids, the radio module, and connectors to the rest of the elements.

2.2.3 Research Hut Computer

In the research hut is a Linux computer that is connected to the infrastructure electronics microcontroller and to a LoRa receiver via USB. This computer collects telemetry data from the whole system, saves it locally, and sends them to an online storage. We are using a web-UI service for IoT applications for ease of monitoring of the system.

2.3 Treatment Algorithms

From a control systems perspective, the solar heater is a dynamic system with 3 measured inputs and one control output. The inputs correspond to the 3 separate temperature measurements at different vertical positions of the tank, and the output is the signal that switches on the solenoid valves, which discharges hot treated effluent and admits cold effluent at the same time.

Figure 2.6. Detailed views of the Solar Water Heater (SWH) unit: (a) Front view showing the elevated stand; (b) Side view showing the thermowell and solenoid valve; (c) Rear view of the assembly; (d) Top view showing the pressure relief valve and sensor; and (e) Bottom view showing the drain valve and secondary sensor.

Figure 2.7. Our UI dashboard hosted on the Thingsboard Cloud

The control object is the maximization of total flow, with the strict condition that the treated effluent should have a pathogen concentration below a certain safety limit.

But because there is no possibility of a real-time observation of output pathogen concentration, we cannot pose a closed-loop control for pathogen concentration. But with a well-studied estimate of what a safe operating range should be, we can easily control for temperature. And vary the system parameters by measuring the pathogen content for each run on those system parameters.

2.3.1 Algorithm 1: Naive Threshold Control

Previous work on drinking water treatment has proposed and tested the simple mechanism of a stratified system that lets out water that reaches some pre-defined threshold temperature, some using solar collectors as a heat source (Koninck *et al.*, 2024) (Duff and Hodgson, 2005). We could employ the same method, which can be summarized as follows:

Algorithm 1 Naive Threshold Control

Require: T_{top} , T_{mid} , T_{bot} ▷ Temperature measurements

Require: T_{th} ▷ Predefined threshold temperature

```
1: Initialize system
2: loop
3:   Measure  $T_{top}$ ,  $T_{mid}$ ,  $T_{bot}$ 
4:   if  $T_{mid} \geq T_{th}$  then
5:     Open valves
6:     Wait for discharge duration
7:     Close valves
8:   end if
9:   Wait for next sampling interval
10: end loop
```

Notice that we compare T_{mid} against T_{th} instead of T_{top} . The reason for this is the geometry of the solar heater. Figure 2.6b shows that the effluent output is on the side of the system. This is pre-defined by the design of the solar water heater that we bought. But because of the upwards going pipe connection at the output, the higher up, and therefore hotter layers of effluent in the stratification end up flowing out of the output. However, because of adhesion, it is inevitable that some effluent from the middle layer will come out. For safety, we check the middle temperature instead of the top.

2.3.2 Algorithm 2: ERT Calculating Algorithm

As introduced in section 1.5, equivalent retention time is a useful concept in pasteurizers with varying temperature. Since our system cannot quantify effluent pathogen content in real-time, we can rely on cumulative ERT as a cursor to the "thermal-dose". Which means that the algorithm looks at the temperature history inside the tank to estimate the pasteurization time at the top of the tank.

This algorithm runs periodically. Let us assume it runs every t seconds. And let us define the amount of time in seconds t corresponds to in 72°C as t_{72} , which is the value we're looking for.

Additionally, we define D_{72} as the amount of time it takes at 72°C for a reduction by 10. We take the average temperature measured in the interval of t seconds to be $x^\circ\text{C}$. Mind that this assumes a linear increase of temperature within that t seconds, which is a fair approximation if t is small enough with respect to the dynamics of the system. Correspondingly D_x will be the amount of time it should take at $x^\circ\text{C}$ for a reduction by 10. These 4 values are related as such:

$$t_{72} = t \cdot D_{72}/D_x \quad (2.1)$$

What is missing in this equation is D_x , which we can interpolate from given values of D from a published dataset. In our implementation, we chose linear interpolation for ease of computation. With values taken from [Espinosa et al., 2020](#), Figure 2.8 visualizes our approach versus logarithmic fitting, which is closer to reality ([Bigelow, 1921](#)). Figure 2.8 visualizes our implementation, where it is visible that the linearly interpolated D-values are larger than the logarithmically interpolated. This results in a more conservative estimation of the retention time due to equation 2.1.

This algorithm assumes perfect stratification, which is a considerable simplification for a system heated from below. This assumption helps us model the process as a batch pasteurization of quantized volumes of effluent, where the hotter the batch, the older it is, and the closer to the top it will be. Or simply put, the tank is assumed to act like a first-in-first-out buffer where the top layer has accumulated the highest thermal dose, while the bottom layer is the most recent untreated effluent.

This algorithm is theoretically more robust because it takes into account lab-tested findings of necessary retention times of certain groups of bacteria to reach a given reduction in pathogen concentrations ([Espinosa et al., 2020](#)). With this information we can base the action of opening the valves to a better guess at the pathogen content.

Figure 2.8. A comparison of linear interpolation and logarithmic fitting on an example set of measured D-values.

Algorithm 2 ERT-Based Control Algorithm (Runs Periodically)

- Require:** T_{top} ▷ Top temperature measurement
- Require:** ERT_{target} ▷ Required retention threshold
- 1: Compute $ERT_{\text{new}} \leftarrow f(T_{\text{top}})$
 - 2: Store ERT_{new} in circular buffer
 - 3: Update accumulated ERT_{sum}
 - 4: **while** $ERT_{\text{sum}} > ERT_{\text{target}}$ **do**
 - 5: Remove oldest valid ERT contribution
 - 6: Update ERT_{sum}
 - 7: Open valves
 - 8: Wait for discharge duration
 - 9: Close valves
 - 10: **end while**
 - 11: Store updated ERT_{sum} and buffer
-

Although we studied and developed the algorithm, we were not able to deploy it in the field due to lack of time in the end. Therefore all test results in the following sections will only portray the naive threshold control with a temperature threshold of 70°C.

2.4 Instrumentation and Data Collection

In order to estimate the states of the solar heater and the systems around it, and to quantify their performance, we collected data from a number of sensors.

All the data we have collected, the scripts we used to analyze them can be found in the project repository ([Polat, Tkaczuk, and Tilley, 2026](#)).

2.4.1 Temperature Measurements

As seen in Figure 2.6c, three temperature sensors are attached to the solar heater tank. These are DS18B20 units, configured for 12-bit resolution with a quantization step of 0.0625°C . The sensor maintains an intrinsic accuracy of $\pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ according to the datasheet ([Integrated, 2019](#)). The solar heater electronics takes measurements from these every 5 minutes. The measurement precision is Additionally, the microcontroller on the solar heater circuit board has an internal temperature sensor ([STMicroelectronics, 2018](#)). The temperature information from this one gives us an idea of how hot the circuit board gets, although the temperature distribution is unequal on the board, where the solar charging circuit is the hottest in most cases. These 4 temperature data points are always published as telemetry data every time they are sampled (every 5 minutes).

Ambient temperature data were obtained from *Solcast* online meteorological datasets ([Solar, Wind and Weather Data Power Built for Renewables | Solcast™ 2026](#)), providing temperature values corresponding to each specific date and time point.

2.4.2 Flow Measurements

We have installed a hall-effect based flow sensor at the output of the effluent storage tank (*RGP-WFS-C-SWNPT* by *DG RGP Industrial Electrical Co. Ltd.*). This produces voltage pulses with a frequency correlating with the flow rate passing through it. The infrastructure electronics microcontroller counts these pulses sends them to the research hut computer, where they are published for monitoring. In order to correlate the pulse frequency of this sensor with an actual flow rate in *L/min*, we needed to calibrate the sensor using a pitcher marked by volume.

There is only one flow sensor for all different outputs from the effluent tank. For this reason, we will only look at the days when the other systems using effluent are not running in our analysis.

Figure 2.9. The heat exchanger. Also visible are the thermowells for inserting thermal sensors, the inlet solenoid valve on the right-hand side, and the electronics box in the background.

2.4.3 Heat Exchanger Efficiency Measurements

Inline thermowells were installed at all inlets and outlets of the heat exchanger as seen in Figure 2.9 in order to be able to place temperature sensors in close contact to the effluent without causing leaks. We performed synchronous measurements by sampling the temperature at 1 Hz at the following points: cold inlet, cold outlet, hot inlet, hot outlet. The gathered data was then processed using the heat exchanger efficiency equation:

$$\epsilon = \frac{T_{h,in} - T_{h,out}}{T_{h,in} - T_{c,in}} \quad (2.2)$$

2.4.4 Illuminance and Irradiation

The performance of solar heaters is dependent on irradiance (Sadhishkumar and Balusamy, 2014). Previous work experimented with taking direct illuminance measurements in a similar setup and found that online irradiance datasets show great correlation with on-site measurements (Lotti, 2025). Because of this, we omitted the measurement of irradiance or illuminance in favor of online datasets from *Solcast*.

2.4.5 Sample Analysis

The samples were taken on-site using sterilized PET bottles. For reference, untreated effluent samples were taken on multiple occasions. The treated samples were taken from the solar heater once it reached the right temperatures to let out the treated effluent. This usually occurred after midday. Microbiological characterization of the samples was performed on-site to determine the inactivation efficiency of the system. The concentration levels of *E. coli* and total coliforms were determined using a dual-method approach, using *LETZTEST* field kits and *IDEXX Tecta B4* automated assays. This comparative analysis allowed for the verification of pathogen reduction in both untreated and treated water samples.

In the *LETZTEST* method, the sample was prepared with a dilution ratio of 99.9 parts water to 0.1 parts effluent, resulting in a sample volume of 100ml. This sample was incubated for 24 hours at a temperature range of 35 – 36°C.

Conversely, the *TECTA* method utilized an undiluted 100ml sample. This second test was subjected to an 18-hour incubation period at a strictly controlled temperature of 35.5°C.

The *TECTA* device has a touchscreen display that prints the measured concentrations, where the *LETZTEST* method involves incubating the diluted sample on a culture, and then counting the resulting colonies (seen as colored dots) using a mobile phone application called *BactLAB* that detects these visually by analyzing a photograph of the test result.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Thermal Performance And Dynamics

3.1.1 Stratification

We have installed 3 temperature sensors at 3 distinct positions at the tank as seen in Figure 2.6. Figure 3.1 shows the temperature measurements on 4 consecutive days in late March. The plots show very strong stratification inside the tank, especially between the middle sensor and the bottom sensor. The average temperature difference between the top and middle points in these 4 days is 5.84°C . However, between the middle and the bottom points this is 43.87°C . The reason for the stark difference might be due to two reasons:

- The bottom temperature sensor is inserted in a thermowell that is protruding out of the tank, hence it is in indirect contact with the ambient temperature. So it will exchange with the colder outside. This cannot be a strong factor because the same holds for the middle sensor.
- The bottom-most part of the tank is below the inlet of the vacuum tubes. This forms a cold "pocket" that stagnates and does not get heated up.

Interesting would be to measure the temperature at the inlet level of the vacuum tubes for future research. Our prediction is that the temperature gradient should be somewhat linear from the top until that level.

Because our treatment strategy is not batch pasteurization, where the whole tank would be filled up and emptied at once, the cold pocket does not pose the risk of untreated cold effluent leaving the system. In our system, only the top level of the as-demonstrated stratified tank can leave. But in case of using batch pasteurization, this stark stratification has to be considered.

CONSECUTIVE TANK TEMPERATURE PROFILE (4 DAYS)

Figure 3.1. Plot that shows the temperature measurements taken from 3 distinct positions at the tank on 4 consecutive days in late March. The measurements show strong stratification.

3.1.2 Nocturnal Heat Loss

Looking at the temperature profile at night shows us the heat insulation capability of the solar heater, since at night there is no incoming heat. However, we should keep in mind that the same heat loss occurs during the day as well.

Figure 3.1 shows that we see significant heat losses during the night. Depending on the day (essentially on how hot the tank is at sunset), the change in temperature at night can exceed 20°C. These findings motivated us to characterize the heat-loss characteristics of the solar heater, since the better the insulation, the more output the solar heater can produce, especially in the early morning hours. This means that improving thermal insulation can increase system throughput.

The governing equations for nocturnal heat loss are the following.

Average power loss equation

$$q_{loss} = \frac{m \cdot C_p \cdot (T_{sunset} - T_{sunrise})}{\Delta t_{night}} \quad (3.1)$$

where q_{loss} is the average power loss during the night in W , m is the total liquid mass in kg (here taken to be 150 kg, since the effluent density is very close to the water density), c_p is the heat capacity in $\frac{J}{kg \cdot K}$ (here taken to be that of water), T_{sunset} and $T_{sunrise}$ are the tank temperatures in K measured in the middle at sunset and sunrise respectively, Δt_{night} is the duration of night in s .

Heat transfer coefficient:

$$h = \frac{q}{A \cdot (T_s - T_f)} \quad (3.2)$$

where h is the heat transfer coefficient in $\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot K}$, A is the surface area of the solar heater in m^2 and T_s and T_f are the tank and ambient temperatures in K , respectively, here taken to be the averages at night on their respective days.

Calculating q_{loss} from 3.1 and putting that into 3.2, we get different values for any recorded day.

ΔT_{drop} (K)	$T_{tank,avg}$ ($^{\circ}C$)	$T_{amb,avg}$ ($^{\circ}C$)	h (W/m^2K)
11.62	82.35	18.97	1.4409
10.56	62.53	19.25	1.9156
16.25	76.61	19.28	2.2275
18.06	59.04	19.83	3.6133
17.62	75.78	18.99	2.4349
12.69	79.28	19.32	1.6598

Table 3.1. Randomly selected nocturnal heat loss parameters from dataset.

Table 3.1 shows data for 6 random days in February and March and the calculated heat transfer coefficient h . The fact that h varies so much from day to day points to the fact that the heat lost through the protruding pipe elements might be more significant than the insulated tank surfaces. Another contributing factor is the climate events that can accelerate heat transfer. Wind and rain have a cooling effect more pronounced than stagnant air.

The solar heater we used is a *RiWatt IronMan 150L*, which comes with a 55mm polyurethane insulation layer inside (*Riwatt IronMan 150L Product Page 2026*). Theoretically, the h value of the solar heater tank should be around 0.6 with the thermal conductivity taken from [Wu, Sung, and Chu, 1999](#), and the thickness taken as 55mm. The calculated values seen in table 3.1 point to the suggestion that the protruding pipe elements should be insulated for better nocturnal heat retention.

Overall, the nocturnal heat loss exceeding $20^{\circ}C$ means that the collected solar energy is being lost to the atmosphere, and further insulation on both the tank and the surrounding piping could yield higher tank temperatures and hence higher throughput.

3.2 Heat Exchanger Validation

In order to test the heat exchanger efficiency, 4 temperature sensors were placed at both inlets and both outlets. The sensors here were chosen to be the same as on the solar heater system, namely: DS18B20.

The experiment was conducted while hot water in the tank was being swapped with cold effluent coming in, and the duration was 9 minutes. Figure 3.2 illustrates the efficiency profile over this 9-minute discharge cycle. It is important to mention that the experiment started from a normal operation of the solar heater. Which means that there was some hot and cold liquid exchange every 5 minutes.

The data reveals three distinct phases:

- Warm-up Phase: Initially, the heat-exchanger is "cold"; the internal plates and the stagnant liquids have to be heated up. The stagnant liquids are not only inside the heat exchanger, but also inside the piping connecting the solar heater to the heat exchanger.
- Peak Effectiveness Phase: With the plates heated up the efficiency is approaching its maximum
- Reducing Effectiveness Phase: After peak, the heat exchanger is no longer able to exchange as much heat due to the incoming hot water becoming colder. This is because of the stratification inside of the tank.

Looking at Figure 3.2, one can see that it reaches maximum efficiency after more than 3 minutes of incessant flow, which is not the case in the normal mode of operation of the solar heater. Normally, the solar heater valves are open only for less than 10 seconds at a time. This means that the heat exchanger operates at a much lower efficiency than it could (around 10%). For the small amounts of flow that occur during normal operation to reach a higher efficiency rate, the heat exchanger and the hot pipes could be insulated. Insulating the heat exchanger will help it retain the heat that it absorbs during the active phase. Similarly, insulating the hot pipes will prevent the hot liquids inside them from exchanging heat with the atmosphere between active phases. Alternatively, a heat exchanger with a higher efficiency could be selected, but this might introduce higher costs.

3.3 Current Consumption

Evaluating the battery voltage changing on a random day (using the naive algorithm 1) as in Figure 3.3, we can see that after sunrise (around 6 AM), the battery is charged in the

Figure 3.2. An efficiency vs. time plot characterizing the heat exchanger. The max efficiency point is marked with a red cross, and the average efficiency over the experiment period (9 minutes) is found to be 0.55

over-charge and float-charge modes, as expected from the operational modes of the battery charging IC CN3767 (Shanghai Consonance Electronics Co, 2026.) It takes until 1 pm for the tank temperature to reach the critical threshold of 70°.

What we see happening while the temperature is above the threshold is that the intervals between the active phases (5 minutes every time in this example) are not enough to bring the battery voltage back up to a charged state. This is one of the limiting factors that reduces the active duration of the valves and hence the device throughput. This phenomenon justifies the orientation of the solar panel as seen in Figure 2.6c. The solar panel should get the most direct sunlight while the tank temperatures are high because that is when more electrical power is needed.

This means that in order to increase the effluent throughput, the power section should be scaled up, or made more efficient. But the higher currents and more active phases will require a reevaluation of the heat management. We should also remember that effluent throughput should increase only then if the output bacterial content is below the safety thresholds.

3.4 Electronics Heat Profile

Figure 3.3 shows an interval a bit before 17:00 where the valves are inactive although the battery voltage is rising. This is due to the microcontroller die temperature being too high, because the device is programmed to become inactive once the microcontroller temperature

Figure 3.3. The battery voltage over a late March day. The naive algorithm is used where the tank temperature threshold is 70°C , and the valves are not opened if the MCU die temperature exceeds 50°C . The red zones are when the valves are opened.

reaches 50°C . This limit was set in order to protect the electrical components from being damaged by overheating.

On the electronics board, it is not the microcontroller that is generating the majority of heat. The primary heat sources are the solar charger circuit and the valve drivers. But there is no temperature sensor directly on those components, so we are using the microcontroller die temperature as a proxy measurement that should pick up the whole PCB heating up from these other heat sources. Currently, there is no active heat dissipation mechanism inside the electronics box. Because of this, it gets heated up both by the sun and the electronics inside. Evidently, this sometimes becomes a limiting factor that reduces the throughput of the system. Which points at the potential benefit of an active heat dissipation mechanism for the electronics box, or a custom electronics box that is capable of passively dissipating the heat.

3.5 Effluent Throughput

The way we measure the amount of effluent through the system is with a hall-effect based flow sensor. We calibrated this sensor in order to map its voltage pulse frequency to flow rate ratio. The result is seen in Figure 3.4. This plot shows the flow readings mapped to L/min with a data point for every second. The data here is from the same day as in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.4. The plot of the flow sensor readings converted to L/min . This plot is taken from the same day as Figure 3.3

Please note that we had an inconsistency issue with the data coming from this sensor, where our initially calibrated parameters ended up not fitting later findings. In one month after calibration, the measured values were up to $0.5L/min$ higher than the actual flow. This might be a continuous degradation and should be addressed in the future. Hence, here we are presenting the sensor values subtracted by that amount. For future use of the sensor data, it should be recalibrated. We also implemented a strict $0.3L/min$ noise floor, which makes sense in the case of the solar heater because its output is modulated by nature. When it outputs, the output is consistently larger than $1L/min$.

Table 3.2. Daily Hydraulic Throughput

Date	Daily Flow (L)
2026-03-23	22.36
2026-03-24	28.33
2026-03-25	25.97
2026-03-26	31.74
2026-03-27	21.81
2026-03-28	21.71
2026-03-29	21.61

As seen in table 3.2, the solar heater produced at least 20 liters in a typical late March week. The amount depends largely on irradiation, which varies throughout the year in Mzuzu as seen in Figure 3.5. Our observations and data collection took place between the months of January and April of 2026, which receive significantly less direct sunlight compared to the "dry" months

Figure 3.5. Mzuzu mean daily sunshine hours for every month, derived from data collected 1961-1990 (*Mzuzu Climate Normals Measured Between 1961-1990 1998* .)

of August, September and October.

3.6 Microbiological Results

Until the last week of our research in Mzuzu, the solar heater was running with water. Only in the last week were we able to do tests with effluent inside the heater. Therefore, we were unable to do extensive tests with more than one set of parameters and more than one valve control algorithm, and so the number of configurations we were able to test is only one. The tests we have performed have been done using the naive algorithm and using 70°C as the tank temperature threshold at the middle sensor.

We took samples from the effluent storage tank and from the solar heater output on multiple days. And we used both of the mentioned measurement devices 2.4 in order to be able to compare them against one another.

Due to scheduling problems and conflict with concurrent measurements a different project at the research site, many of the samples that were taken could not be tested on the same day. And since there is no fridge there, this rendered those samples unusable. This left us with a small number of microbiological results.

Table 3.3 shows the results we obtained using our two methods. The table shows the date the corresponding samples were taken, where the sample was taken from, what the test method was and what the *E. Coli* and *Total Coliform* concentrations were. The last 4 entries show the inconsistency of the two methods. Where the *LetzTest* method shows 4000 colony forming units

of *E. Coli* per 100ml, the *TECTA* method finds none. This finding undermines the integrity of our microbiological findings.

The two *LetzTest* tests that were conducted on April 7th show that the *E. Coli* concentration in the effluent tower is lower than in the solar heater output. This might be due to contamination during the test.

On the other hand, the stark reduction in the *E. Coli* concentrations seen in the *LetzTest* results from March 10th to March 30th is a sign that the solar heater environment might be successfully reducing pathogen concentrations.

Table 3.3. Comparison of *E. coli* and Total Coliform concentrations in the Solar Heater and Effluent Tower (Samples tested within 3 days of collection). The *E.Coli* and Total Coliform concentrations are given by the number of colony forming units per 100ml.

Date	Test Method	Location	<i>E. coli</i>	Total Coliforms
2026-03-10	LetzTest	Effluent Tower	360,000	N/A
2026-03-10	LetzTest	Solar Heater	311,000	N/A
2026-03-23	LetzTest	Solar Heater	33,000	N/A
2026-03-30	LetzTest	Solar Heater	4,000	N/A
2026-03-30	TECTA	Solar Heater	< 1	< 1
2026-04-07	LetzTest	Solar Heater	4,000	N/A
2026-04-07	LetzTest	Effluent Tower	2,000	N/A
2026-04-07	TECTA	Solar Heater	< 1	< 1
2026-04-07	TECTA	Effluent Tower Tank	< 1	89

3.7 Cost Analysis

For successful deployment in low-income contexts, the cost of the solar heater was aimed to be as low as possible. Additionally, to make repair and maintenance easier, we used locally sourced components whenever possible.

When it comes to calculating the cost, the solar heater system cannot be taken just on its own, because it could not operate without its surrounding infrastructure. As explained in [Lotti, 2025](#) and [Cinar, 2025](#), as long as there is not enough steepness in the installation area, there needs to be an active pumping mechanism that carries effluent to the solar heater. Also in our site there was no significant slope. But this condition is desired for the *Sistema.Bio* biogas digesters, therefore the active pumping mechanism should be addressed in most cases, except the case where the solar heater is dug down, but this comes with extra difficulties such as rainwater buildup, limitation of possible sunlight angles, increased construction costs etc.

Even so, we will analyze the total system cost by separating the solar heater costs and the required infrastructure costs.

Component	Cost in CHF
Lead Acid Battery (M)	17
Solar Panel (M)	13.1
Computer in the hut (M)	75.6
Solar heater installation(M)	40
Printed circuit board (C)	63.8
Solar water heater(M)	558.4
LoRa receiver (C)	2.99
Solenoid valves (C)	32.97
Heat exchanger (E)	41.89
Temperature sensors(C)	7.02
Thermowells (C)	3
Lora receiver microcontroller (C)	10.5
electronics box (M)	1.8
Total	868.07

Table 3.4. A cost breakdown of the solar heater and the parts around it. Next to the component names are what country they were acquired in. **E** stands for Europe, **C** stands for China. Both of these are online orders. **M** stands for Malawi and these were either bought from the markets in Mzuzu, or in direct contact with sellers.

Table 3.4 shows the cost breakdown for the solar heater in isolation. The prices have been converted to *CHF* with the conversion rates on April 3rd 2026. What stands out is the high cost of the solar water heater, especially in comparison to previous work done by Cinar, 2025 and Lotti, 2025. Ours is around two times as expensive as what they paid. Although other sellers in Mzuzu told us this is a reasonable price for a 150L solar heater, we think it should be possible to find a better deal.

The table does not include the costs of cables that we used, since this is heavily dependent on the dimensions of the deployment area. Still it is worth to mention that we paid between 0.2 CHF to 0.3 CHF per meter in Mzuzu, depending on the wire gauge.

The most important complementary infrastructure elements are the pump, effluent storage tank and the control electronics around these. If the deployment site has a natural incline, these elements will not be necessary, and the total cost will be lower.

The plumbing parts are assumed to be as simple (hence also) cheap as they can be. Previous work suggests the use of polypropylene pipes for their heat tolerance.

3.8 Discussion

3.8.1 Thermal Dynamics and Pasteurization Efficiency

The temperature measurements confirm that there is stratification inside the solar heater tank with most of the tank staying well above favorable temperatures for E. Coli (Blaustein *et al.*, 2013). This confirms that the temperature stratification should not halt pathogen inactivation. However, we were unable to verify this because of the shortcoming in our microbiological measurement methods. In the presence of a sound microbiological measurement method, the system could be tuned until the output is pathogen-free.

We have seen that significant nighttime heat losses occurred from the system. This could be addressed by improving the heat insulation around the system.

3.8.2 Power and Heat Management

We have seen that on hotter and sunnier days, the power generated by the solar panel was insufficient to keep the battery voltage from collapsing. This caused a reduced valve activation. Using the naive algorithm, it should be theoretically possible to bring the tank temperature down to the threshold temperature by a prolonged opening of the valves. But whether this is permissible can only be seen through microbial analysis. If the output is not pathogen-free, the effluent throughput should not be increased.

The current enclosure for the solar heater electronics falls short of dissipating the heat generated by the circuit. For an increased throughput, this will have to be addressed as well. Potentially, a redesign of the circuit board with more efficient components might also be beneficial in this regard by generating less heat.

3.8.3 Controls

The construction works at the research site and the long duration of pathogen removal and microbiological tests left us with insufficient time to tune and test multiple control algorithms. Based on previous work, the naive algorithm has a good chance of working successfully, but this has to be verified and if necessary, tuned.

3.8.4 Microbiological Results

Our microbiological results showed that the two measurement methods that we employed gave us incoherent results. This incoherency should be studied and ideally, a reference method

should be found in order to determine whether either of the in-house methods is faulty (or both).

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Building upon previous research, this study evaluated the feasibility of utilizing a commercial solar water heater to pasteurize anaerobic digester effluent in Mzuzu, Malawi. The primary objective was to optimize the balance between maximizing hydraulic throughput and ensuring total pathogen inactivation. The research focused on the system's internal thermal state, the performance of the custom control electronics, and the resulting microbiological quality of the treated effluent, and the exploration of multiple control methods linking temperature measurements to valve control. As lateral goals we had cost minimization, off-grid operation, and ease of remote monitoring.

The thermal analysis of the system revealed significant vertical stratification within the tank, where the top of the tank regularly reached temperatures above 80°C , but a stagnant cold pocket below the vacuum tube inlets. Our assumption was that because the system operates on a basis of continuous pasteurization, the cold pocket is of no serious consequence. But this assumption could not be tested because of the incomplete bacterial analysis.

Using a "naive" control algorithm where the system starts letting out effluent above a 70°C threshold, the system processed over 20 liters of effluent per day during late March. While LetzTest results indicated a reduction in *E. coli* concentrations compared to the effluent tower, our findings were complicated by incoherency between measurement methods. Specifically, the TECTA method found no pathogens where the LetzTest found $4,000\text{ CFU}/100\text{ml}$. Consequently, while the 70°C threshold shows promise, a 99.9% reduction cannot be definitively confirmed without further testing of varied control parameters against a trustworthy reference bacterial measurement method.

In terms of measuring the solar heater tank, our sensor configuration utilized three sensors at different depths of the solar heater tank, where the bottom one was not utilized in any control approach. Additional sensor nodes crucial to the system's controls were the PCB temperature measurement and the battery voltage measurement. The naive algorithm imitates a temperature activated outlet valve that has been previously demonstrated to successfully work in water inactivation schemes, and utilizes only one temperature sensor. Successful bacterial inactivation using the naive algorithm would prove the sufficiency of having one sensor at the tank, and we have data that point to this possibility. However, more rigorous microbiological

tests are necessary for a conclusion.

The custom electronics provided a stable logging platform, but the system struggled with power and heat management during peak hours. Power consumption of the solenoid valves often exceeded the instantaneous solar charging rate, leading to battery depletion. Additionally, the device frequently hit a 50°C safety shutdown due to internal electronics heating during the periods of highest solar irradiation. For a self-sufficient system with higher throughput, scaling the power section and improving heat dissipation for the electronics box are mandatory prerequisites.

The total system cost was around 870 CHF, with the commercial solar water heater representing nearly two-thirds of the expenditure. This price is approximately twice as high as previous research in the region, which may limit viability in low-income contexts.

Future work should focus on conducting more tests with varying parameters and control methods while microbiologically analyzing the processed effluent in these varying device modes. The two microbiological test methods that we used seem to be incoherent with one another, which gives room for suspicion to the results. For better integrity of the microbiological results, a trustworthy measurement method as a reference is necessary. Device bottlenecks should be identified and addressed, two examples being: scaling up the power system, and improving heat dissipation. In addition, better heat insulation on the tank, the pipes and the heat exchanger will be beneficial to improve heat retention and therewith improve pasteurization conditions.

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